

Effect of Ultrasonic Waves on the Catalytic Activity of Hydrous Zirconium Oxide

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The surface of hydrous zirconium oxide is modified by agitating it with supersonic waves. It is observed that the samples of this hydrous oxide age under the influence of these waves. The ageing is accompanied by an increase in the hydrogen ion concentration of the suspensions and a decrease in the catalytic activity of the latter towards the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solution. The loss in the catalytic activity is accompanied by the formation of a stable true peroxy compound of zirconium, viz., $ZrO_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, in the system.

It has been repeatedly emphasised from these laboratories that the ultrasonic agitation of various gel-forming systems prevents the formation of large aggregates.¹ Numerous workers have investigated the depolymerising action of supersonic waves on various substances.² Mushran and co-workers³ have studied the effect of ultrasonic energy on the pH, conductivity and stability of several organo-metallic sols and established that anything that discourages structuration helps in retarding the gelation. Ven'chzhoi and co-workers⁴ have reported that ultrasonic radiations can either raise or lower the catalytic activity by causing a change in the particle size of the catalyst. Krause and co-workers⁵ have observed that aluminium oxide hydrate ages under the influence of high power supersonic waves. The aging of the hydrated oxide is established by means of some catalytic reactions, activated by Co^{+2} /Aluminium Oxide hydrate carriers, especially the oxidation of indigo carmine by hydrogen peroxide.

In the present paper we have investigated the influence of ultrasonic agitation on the catalytic activity of different samples of hydrous zirconium oxide towards the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ultrasonic Apparatus: The source of ultrasonic power was a Mullard's high frequency ultrasound generator of the type E-7562 coupled with a barium titanate transducer. The electrical input to the transducer, with a frequency of 1 Mc/sec., was 225 Watts per sq.

1. Prakash et al., *Kolloid-Z.*, 1958, 160, 33. *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 306. *Kolloid-Z.*, 1961, 175, 56; 1963, 190, 60, 136. *Talanta.*, 1964, 11, 1113.
2. Liu and Wu, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 701; 1934, 56, 1006. Sato and Nakasima, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1949 18, 331.
3. Mushran et al., *Kolloid-Z.*, 1960, 171, 31. *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 404. *Rheol. Acta.*, 1964, 3, 310.
4. Ven'chzhoi et al., *Zhur. fiz. Khim.*, 1964, 39, 80.
5. Krause et al., *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1963, 318, 9.

cm. The crystal was immersed in a constantly circulating water bath maintained at a temperature of 30° and the distance between the vessel and the transducer was so adjusted as to get a maximum fountain. The R.F. output voltage was maintained constant at 1.8 K.V.

Three different samples A, B and C of hydrous zirconium oxide were prepared by adding 10% deficient, equivalent and 10% excess quantities, respectively, of $0.5882M$ solution of sodium hydroxide (A.R., B.D.H.) to a fixed volume of $0.5876M$ aqueous solution of zirconium nitrate (pure variety). These precipitations were carried out in Jena glass bottles maintained at a temperature of $31 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in a constantly circulating water-bath. The samples were thoroughly washed with distilled water until free from the occluded electrolytes and estimated for their zirconia (ZrO_2) content separately. The samples were suitably diluted so as to contain 0.05 gm. of zirconia per 10 ml. of the suspension.

50 ml. of the suspension was exposed to ultrasonic energy for different time-intervals. After each exposure the pH of the suspensions was measured by employing a L and N type pH-meter fitted with a glass electrode. 10 ml. of the sonically agitated suspension of hydrous zirconium oxide was subsequently used to catalyze the decomposition of $0.02N$ solution of hydrogen peroxide (Merckozone). The effect of pH changes on the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide was avoided by adding 20 ml. of buffer (pH=6.0; acetic acid + sodium acetate) solution to the reaction mixture. The total volume of the reaction mixture was raised to 100 ml. by adding distilled water. The kinetic investigations were carried out at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The photochemical decomposition of hydrogen peroxide was prevented by wrapping the reaction bottle in a black opaque cloth.

The effect of ultrasonic agitation on the catalytic activity of the sample A of hydrous zirconium oxide, which was precipitated by employing 10% deficient amount

FIG. 1 Time (min.)

of alkali, towards the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide is represented in the Fig. 1. Similar plots of $\log(a/a-x)$ against 't' can be obtained for the samples B and C of hydrous zirconium oxide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is interesting to observe that a colloidal dispersion of hydrous zirconium oxide is obtained when the samples of the latter are subjected to prolonged irradiation with high power ultrasonic waves of frequency 1 Mc/Sec. A transparent sol of this hydrous oxide is obtained which readily flocculates in presence of electrolytes such as KCl and $BaCl_2$. Numerous workers⁶ in this field have attributed such depolymerising action of supersonic waves to the phenomenon of cavitation which involves the formation and subsequent collapsing of vapour bubbles in the system with sufficient violence. Therefore, it appears that as soon as the gelatinous precipitate of hydrous zirconium oxide is charged with supersonic waves the coherent structure of the particles is shattered down owing to the onergetic high frequency ultrasound waves which cause a tremendous mechanical agitation of the particles. It is also observed that an appreciable decrease in the pH of the suspensions of hydrous zirconium oxide is brought about when the samples of the latter are charged with ultrasonic energy (c.f. table 1).

TABLE I

Effect of ultrasonic waves on the pH of the suspensions of hydrous zirconium oxide

Exposure (hra.)	A	pH B	C
0	8.75	8.60	8.60
1	8.40	8.20	8.30
2	7.85	7.65	7.80
3	7.45	6.25	7.40

It is evident from a perusal of the above Table that the hydrogen ion concentration of the suspensions of hydrous zirconium oxide is greatly increased on exposing the latter to supersonic waves. Extensive investigations have been carried out in the field of ultrasonics by Prakash and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) in these laboratories. These workers have repeatedly emphasised the oxidising properties of ultrasonic waves in the presence of dissolved oxygen. This has been attributed by these workers to the activation of oxygen by ultrasonic energy according to the following equation:

During the present investigations it appears that the activated oxygen generated in the system probably reacts with hydrous zirconium oxide, when the latter is irradiated with ultrasonic waves, to form an unstable peroxy zirconic acid (H_2ZrO_4) as follows:

6. Prudhomme and Graber, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, 46, 667.

O^* —activated oxygen.

Ionisation of zirconic acid (H_2ZrO_4) takes place stepwise according to the following equation;

and finally a true peroxy compound of zirconium, which is stable in nature, is formed as follows:

The hydrogen ions generated in the system, according to the equation (3) above, are responsible for bringing about a decrease in the pH of the suspensions of hydrous zirconium oxide. Simultaneously with the generation of H^+ ions in the system $HZrO_4^-$ ions are also released. These OH^- ions and $HZrO_4^-$ ions, either separately or jointly, are responsible for providing the necessary charge towards the stabilisation of the colloidal particles of hydrous zirconium oxide.

The ultrasonically irradiated samples of hydrous zirconium oxide were placed in sunlight for some time to decompose the traces of hydrogen peroxide which is formed during the sonic agitation. These samples were subsequently used to catalyse the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solution. The process of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by the fresh as well as ultrasonically agitated samples of hydrous zirconium oxide is found to be of first order and the average values of the first order velocity constants ($k/2 \cdot 303$) for the decomposition of 0.02 *N* solution of hydrogen peroxide catalysed by the fresh as well as sonically agitated samples of hydrous zirconium oxide are presented in the following table:

TABLE 2

Effect of ultrasonic waves on the catalytic activity of hydrous zirconium oxide

Exposure (hrs.)	First order velocity constants ($k/2 \cdot 303$)		
	A	B	C
0	71.89	56.98	64.60
2	65.67	54.96	59.18
8	64.04	53.28	57.84

It is clearly seen from a perusal of the above table and also from the Fig. 1 that the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide is retarded when catalysed by the samples of hydrous zirconium oxide exposed to ultrasonic radiations. Since finer particles of this hydrous oxide in the form of a colloidal dispersion are obtained when the suspensions of the former are agitated by the mechanical action of the supersonic waves, thereby resulting in increase in the available surface area of the catalyst, it is expected that a slight increase in the percentage decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, during a definite time-interval, would be brought about. On the contrary, a decrease in the catalytic activity of the irradiated samples is observed towards the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solution. This anomalous observation is attributed to the partial formation of a catalytically less

active stable true peroxy compound of zirconium, viz., $ZrO_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, as according to the equation (4) mentioned earlier. The decrease in the catalytic activity of the samples is also ascribed to the expulsion of water molecules from the interstitial spaces of the particles of hydrous zirconium oxide when the latter is mechanically agitated by high power supersonic waves. These water molecules are believed to form the seats of catalysis on the surface of this hydrous oxide. The decrease in the catalytic activity is also attributed to the 'blocking' of the active centres on the surface of hydrous zirconium oxide due to preferential adsorption of hydroxyl ions which are released in the system.

It will appear from a perusal of the Fig. 1 that the values of $\log(a/a-x)$, where 'a' and 'a-x' represent the initial concentration and the concentration after time 't' of hydrogen peroxide, increase rapidly at the beginning of the reaction. In fact, as soon as the gelatinous precipitate of hydrous zirconium oxide comes in contact with hydrogen peroxide an unstable true peroxy compound of zirconium is formed.' This compound is very active towards the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and eventually changes to a stable true peroxy compound of Zirconium, $ZrO_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, which is catalytically less active. The formation of this compound in the system has been confirmed by isolating the ultimate product of the reaction. The product is found to liberate iodine from a solution of potassium iodide and to consume some potassium permanganate in the presence of sulphuric acid. These properties are similar to those of potassium peroxydisulphate which is a true peroxy compound.

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